

The Philosophical Sketch of Gravitation Origin

Konstantin M. Golubev

State Space Agency of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine

Corresponding email: gkm@nkau.gov.ua

ORCID ID:0000-0003-2929-1932

This article presents a philosophical view on gravitation origin, based on the ideas of independent quasi-elastic collisions of very small energy particles and relatively big particles. Aim is to show that moderate shift in philosophy from physics paradigm about “empty space with pointlike particles” could lead to significant shift in reality explanation including explanation of light velocity limit, almost instant gravitation interaction, particle-wave duality and uncertainty principle. This study proposes universal foundation for both Standard Model and Quantum Mechanics. It is interdisciplinary with attention to progress in physics, mathematics, philosophy, logic and would be interesting for all people relied on gravitation in their activities.

Keywords: gravitation origin; Le Sage; Nicolas Fatio; Van Flandern; Isaac Newton;

Introduction

"Unthinking respect for authority is the greatest enemy of truth." Albert Einstein

Should a paradigm be changed..? Anyway paradigm is changing at times. Ptolemy's system was so effective at predicting positions in the night sky that was used to prepare astronomical and astrological charts for over 1,500 years. The only flaw was incorrect image of universe.

Old Greek paradigm “Nothing exists except atoms and empty space; everything else is opinion” is looking like absolutely arbitrary proposition not proved in any sense. But we see traces of this thought in many branches of science. Known physicist Brian Greene said in his book [1] that “...standard model views the elementary constituents of the universe as pointlike ingredients with no internal structure.”

According to present-day understanding of what is called the vacuum state or the quantum vacuum, it is "by no means a simple empty space...According to quantum mechanics, the vacuum state is not truly empty but instead contains fleeting electromagnetic waves and particles that pop into and out of existence... In fact, the energy of a cubic centimeter of empty space has been calculated figuratively to be one trillionth of an erg (or 0.6 eV)." [2]

Isaac Newton did not explain how gravity propagates: “Gravity must be caused by an agent [acting] consta[ntly] according to certain laws, but whether this agent be material or immaterial is a question I have left to the consideration of my readers.”

Albert Einstein postulated curved empty space, but did not explain how nothing could be curved. The strictest criterion to define a vacuum is a region of space and time where all the components of the stress–energy tensor are zero. This means that this region is devoid of energy and momentum, and by consequence, it must be empty of particles and other physical fields (such as electromagnetism) that contain energy and momentum.

It seems evident that nothing cannot fluctuate. Respectively the universe has no empty parts where nothing exists. And total universe natural medium with some energetic value is present, in which all known objects are living.

Physicist Robert Laughlin, the 1998 Nobel Laureate in Physics, who said this about aether in 2005: “It is ironic that Einstein’s most creative work, the general theory of relativity, should boil down to conceptualizing space as a medium when his original premise [in special relativity] was that no such medium existed. [...] The word ‘aether’ has extremely negative connotations in theoretical physics because of its past association with opposition to relativity. This is unfortunate because, stripped of these connotations, it rather nicely captures the way most physicists actually think about the vacuum. [...] The modern concept of the vacuum of space, confirmed every day by experiment, is a relativistic aether.” [5]

Materials and Methods

The physicists say that physical particles communicate using messenger particles providing interaction. It looks like any physical particle is surrounded by a cloud of messenger particles to the significant, even infinite distance. And that the empty universe should be filled with these messenger particles.

Brian Greene [1] said about “Messenger Particles...The standard model instructs us to think of these force particles as having no internal structure...The photons, gluons, and weak gauge bosons provide the microscopic mechanism for transmitting the forces they constitute...An electromagnetic field is composed of a swarm of photons; the interaction between two charged particles actually arises from their "shooting" photons back and forth between themselves...two oppositely charged particles also interact through the exchange of photons, although the resulting electromagnetic force is attractive. It's as if the photon is not so much the transmitter of the force per se, but rather the transmitter of a message of how the recipient must respond to the force in question. For like-charged particles, the photon carries the message "move apart," while for oppositely charged particles it carries the message "come together." For this reason the photon is sometimes referred to as the messenger particle for the electromagnetic force. Similarly, the gluons and weak gauge bosons are the messenger particles for the strong and weak nuclear forces. The strong force, which keeps quarks locked up inside of protons and neutrons, arises from individual quarks exchanging gluons. The gluons, so to speak, provide the "glue" that keeps these subatomic particles stuck together. The weak force, which is responsible for certain kinds of particle transmutations involved in radioactive decay, is mediated by the weak gauge bosons.”

We could suggest that gravitation force is not mediated by messenger particles, but it is a feature of a non-empty space filled with independently moving small energy particles, not observable directly now due to their very little size. It is an idea not

exceeding by strangeness the messenger particles idea. And the only suggestion that universe is filled with very little energy particles would be leading to the following propositions:

(1) *The velocity of massive observable objects should be restricted by maximum value, like restricted in any dense habitat, water, as an example;*

“Q: Why is hitting water from a great height like hitting concrete? Physicist: There’s nothing terribly special about water, and even hitting a gas fast enough would “feel like concrete”. For example, when meteors (which are fast) hit the atmosphere they generally shatter immediately. A good way to think about high-velocity impacts is not in terms of things (like water) acting more solid, but in terms of things (like people, rocks, Fabergé eggs) acting more fluid. The more energy that’s involved in a collision, the less important the binding energy (the energy required to pull a thing apart) is. A general, hand-wavy rule of thumb is: if the random kinetic energy of a piece of material is greater than the binding energy, then the material will behave like a fluid. A bit more energy and it will fly apart.” [3] Also we’ll get shortening effect at high speed due to increasing pressure from energy particles at a massive object head, and object mass raise due to shadow effect.

(2) *The massive objects should be attracted by any massive object, and it is a property of medium, not objects;*

Plasma is loosely described as an electrically neutral medium of unbound positive and negative particles (i.e. the overall charge of plasma is roughly zero)... Electrons, ions, protons and neutrons can be distinguished by the sign and value of their charge so that they behave independently in many circumstances, with different bulk velocities and temperatures... Collisional interactions are often weak in hot plasmas and external forcing can drive the plasma far from local equilibrium and lead to a significant population of unusually fast particles (Wikipedia). Dubinov A. E. et al state “Various theoretical studies have now been published in the scientific literature in which several different forces of attraction have been proposed and analyzed, among which we note the following: 1) Attraction whose mechanism is based on the asymmetric bombardment of a dust particle by plasma particles caused by shadowing of this dust particle by neighboring ones;... To sum up, these experimental results indicate that forces of attraction of a nonelectrical nature are observed between adjacent macroscopic bodies in a plasma, and these determine the dynamics of these bodies.” [4]

“The elastic scattering of a neutron by collision with an atomic nucleus is similar to that of a billiard ball colliding with another billiard ball. A portion of the kinetic energy of one particle is transferred to the other without loss of kinetic energy in the process... This process of interaction of neutrons with matter results only in scattering of the neutron and recoil nucleus.”[6]

The Einstein’s idea of curved empty space is an abstraction. But medium can have density fluctuations, with less dense areas around massive objects due to shadow effect. It is explanation of a gravitation interaction.

(3) *The massive objects should have particle-wave duality, like any ship in a sea surrounded with waves;*

In a space filled with moving energy particles solid body should be accompanied with waves of energy particles.

(4) *The exact position of massive object should be uncertain due to collisions with small particles;*

It is called uncertainty principle in physics.

Mathematical Foundation

Almost all known at the moment mass affected by gravitation is located in protons/neutrons. We can consider one proton in a space. The picture is looking this way [Fig. 1].

Figure 1. Proton in a space

From proton's point of view all energy particles fly toward to the proton [Fig. 2]. Their hits are compensated and cause a jittering; it looks like uncertainty principle in action. We should propose that hits presented are not like dumb balls collisions hits, but complex interactions like quasi-elastic collisions.

Figure 2. Interaction of solid body and proton

But, if a solid body is present near the proton, it should serve as a shield stopping energy particles flow in a sector of space. The proton does the same for the body. The number of non-compensated energy particles from left side cone pushing the body toward the proton ($G-L$) is equal to a number of non-compensated energy particles from right side cone pushing the proton toward the body ($G-R$). Suppose that mass of the proton is 1 for simplicity. Number of non-compensated energy particles should be proportional to the number of protons/neutrons in the solid body mI (body mass) because every proton/neutron can stop/decline the energy particle. This number does not depend on a shape of body because volume of atom's nuclei is about 1,000,000,000,000 times less than atom's volume.

Every pushing in intelligent collision energy particle may give a bit of acceleration to the proton or the body. The body's acceleration toward the proton should be less than proton's acceleration toward the body in a proportion of its mass (protons/neutrons number) because the same force/effect (hitting energy particles number/sec) applied to both.

Figure 3. Interaction at greater distance of solid body and proton

If the body and the proton appear to be at greater distance then initially - $(G-L)$ | $(G-R)$ forces should become smaller due to lesser size of shield effect stopping lesser number of energy particles moving towards proton [Fig. 3]. Number of non-compensated energy particles should be proportional to the 2-dimensional shield area of solid body, depending on total number of energy particles moving towards proton, but not on a distance of stopped energy particle from the proton.

Initial shield sector for the proton $b3$ is the 2-dimensional solid body projection $a1a2$ at distance $b2b3$.

After solid body $a1a2$ moves to $b4b5$ place, distance appears $b1b3$, and shield sector appears to be $a3a4$.

$a1a2r$ (sector $a1a2$ radius) = $b4b5r$ (sector $b4b5$ radius). $a3a4r$ = sector $a3a4$ radius.

Suppose for simplicity that initial distance $b2b3$ between the proton and the body 1m.

Resulting distance r after moving is $b1b3$.

$$(a3a4r/b4b5r) = (a3a4r/a1a2r) = (1/b1b3) = 1/r$$

$$Aa3a4 \text{ (Area of sector } a3a4) = \pi \cdot (a3a4r)^2$$

$$Aa1a2 \text{ (Area of sector } a1a2) = \pi \cdot (a1a2r)^2$$

$$(Aa3a4)/(Aa1a2) = (\pi*(a3a4r)^2)/(\pi*(a1a2)^2) = (a3a4r/a1a2r)^2 = 1/r^2$$

$Aa3a4$ (Area of shield sector after moving $a3a4$) / $Aa1a2$ (Area of initial shield sector $a1a2$) = $1/r^2$

After moving $(G-L)$ | $(G-R)$ decreases in a proportion of r^2 where r is resulting distance between the body and the proton.

We think that in this case there is a force proportional to the mass of the solid body $m1$ and inversely proportional to the square of the distance r^2 that pushing the body to the proton and the proton to the body.

$$(G-L) | (G-R) = (\text{some constant for calibration}) * m1 / r^2$$

If we consider instead of a proton one more solid body with $m2$ protons/neutrons we'll get number of non-compensated energy particles from left $(G-L2) = (G-L) * m2$. $(G-R2) = (G-R) * m2$.

$$(G-L2) | (G-R2) = (\text{some constant for calibration}) * m1 * m2 / r^2$$

And how it can be compared with this presentation? [Fig. 4]

Figure 4. "NewtonsLawOfUniversalGravitation" by I, Dennis Nilsson. Licensed under CC BY 3.0 via Wikimedia Commons

(<http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:NewtonsLawOfUniversalGravitation.svg#/media/File:NewtonsLawOfUniversalGravitation.svg>)

- where: F is the force between the masses; G is the gravitational constant; $m1$ is the first mass; $m2$ is the second mass; r is the distance between the centers of the masses.

Results

Objections to shadow theory of gravitation are based on the energy and heat issue. Inelastic collisions should lead to a vaporization of matter within fractions of a second. If we suppose that interactions are quasi-elastic [6], the interactions keep objects stable.

The philosophy behind physics supposes that if the mathematics built on certain philosophical assumption gives good prediction, it means that philosophical assumption

is true and proven. The case of Ptolemy's system shows that it is not right assertion. The good prediction power of mathematical model of universe does not prove viability of initial philosophy.

At the moment physics is relying on a philosophy of pointlike particles and empty space. The heavy mathematics around this philosophy describes pointlike particles interactions, that are exchanging with bunches of virtual messenger particles, in a curved emptiness space limiting velocity of objects and giving power of attraction and mass increasing. And this curved emptiness produces virtual particles, in principle readily staying as real particles.

If we consider philosophy of space as a medium filled with very little energy particles, we'll get the following picture:

- (1) The velocity of massive objects should be restricted by maximum value, like it is restricted in any dense habitat, water, as an example;
- (2) The massive objects should be attracted by any object, and it is a property of medium, not objects;
- (3) The massive objects should have particle-wave duality, like any ship in a sea surrounded with water waves;
- (4) The exact position of massive object should be uncertain due to collisions with small particles;
- (5) The medium should be curved due to density variations;
- (6) The known likeness of acceleration and gravitation, shown in Einstein's analogy of human in accelerating lift, could be explained by collisions with small energy particles that cause acceleration in direction that negative to movement continuously;
- (7) Both virtual particle and antiparticle should have a positive energy existing even one picosecond, because they could easily remain as stable particles if separated instantly. And negative energy is mathematical abstraction, not reflecting any real phenomenon. Both electron and positron have positive energy level/mass, but opposite electrical signs.

Discussion

“Nicolas Fatio de Duillier (alternative names are Facio or Faccio; 26 February 1664 – 12 May 1753) was a Swiss mathematician known for his work on the zodiacal light problem, for his very close relationship with Isaac Newton, for his role in the Newton v. Leibniz calculus controversy, and for originating the "push" or "shadow" theory of gravitation...This theory...is based on minute particles which push gross matter to each other.” (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nicolas_Fatio_de_Duillier)

“Daniel Bernoulli was pleased by the similarity of Le Sage's model and his own thoughts on the nature of gases. However, Bernoulli himself had the opinion that his

own kinetic theory of gases was only a speculation, and likewise he regarded Le Sage's theory as highly speculative.”

“Partly in consideration of Le Sage's theory, Pierre-Simon Laplace undertook to determine the necessary speed of gravity in order to be consistent with astronomical observations. He calculated that the speed must be “at least a hundred millions of times greater than that of light”, in order to avoid unacceptably large inequalities due to aberration effects in the lunar motion. This was taken by most researchers, including Laplace, as support for the Newtonian concept of instantaneous action at a distance.”

“A basic prediction of the theory is the extreme porosity of matter...This prediction has been (in some respects) confirmed over the course of the time. Indeed, matter consists mostly of empty space and certain particles like neutrinos can pass through matter nearly unhindered.”

“As noted in the historical section, a major problem for every Le Sage model is the energy and heat issue. As Maxwell and Poincaré showed, inelastic collisions lead to a vaporization of matter within fractions of a second and the suggested solutions were not convincing. For example, Aronson gave a simple proof of Maxwell's assertion.”

And Tom Van Flandern said: “General relativity (GR) explains these features by suggesting that gravitation (unlike electromagnetic forces) is a pure geometric effect of curved space-time, not a force of nature that propagates. Gravitational radiation, which surely does propagate at lightspeed but is a fifth order effect in, is too small to play a role in explaining this difference in behavior between gravity and ordinary forces of nature. Problems with the causality principle also exist for GR in this connection, such as explaining how the external fields between binary black holes manage to continually update without benefit of communication with the masses hidden behind event horizons. These causality problems would be solved without any change to the mathematical formalism of GR, but only to its interpretation, if gravity is once again taken to be a propagating force of nature in flat space-time with the propagation speed indicated by observational evidence and experiments: not less than 2×10^{10} c. Such a change of perspective requires no change in the assumed character of gravitational radiation or its lightspeed propagation.”

http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tom_Van_Flander

Conclusions

“Van Flandern supported Le Sage's theory of gravitation, according to which gravity is the result of a flux of invisible "ultra-mundane corpuscles" impinging on all objects from all directions at superluminal speeds. He gave public lectures in which he claimed that these particles could be used as a limitless source of free energy, and to provide superluminal propulsion for spacecraft. In 1998 Van Flandern wrote a paper asserting that astronomical observations imply that gravity propagates at least twenty billion times faster than light.” http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tom_Van_Flander

The hypothesis of very little fast independently moving energy particles filling a space could be verified by an experiment. If we could accelerate protons in a space called vacuum at near light velocity, but accelerating force at chosen time stops. Protons velocity should be measured during defined time observing changes in their degree. If

velocity decreases, it would indicate that a force appears applied against protons movement direction. It would justify existence of very little fast independently moving energy particles, because number of interacted little particles at the heads of protons should be greater than elsewhere.

If it is right the universe appears not very big, as supposed previously. The gravitation unites any parts of Milky Way galaxy through gravity interaction in less than 3 minutes. Also the gravitation unites any parts of whole universe through gravity interaction in less than 6 years.

“Universe	
Diameter	Possibly infinite, at least 91 billion light-years
Volume	At least 4×10^{83} liters
Mass (ordinary matter)	At least 10^{53} kg
Shape	Flat with only a 0.4% margin of error”

<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Universe>

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